

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 5.1 Project Management Plan, M24

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

This is a Horizon Europe project (Coordination and Support Action) funded by the European Union for 3 years (from 1 July 2022 until 30 June 2025).

Project summary

Support Stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9.

The overarching goal of this project is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platforms (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan.

Supporting the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders – including industry, researchers, public authorities, civil society – in order to accelerate the delivery of the CCUS research and innovation (R&I) activities and to progress the emerging policy priorities at EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS, will be crucial over the coming years for Europe to reach the ambitious climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

This will be achieved by efficiently aligning and coordinating the activities of ETIP ZEP and the IWG9 in a joint work programme; establishing networks and other fora to enable the stakeholders to collaborate and coordinate effectively, pooling expertise, experience and resources to address common challenges; engaging also with other programmes and external stakeholders; facilitating engagement and creating greater interaction and cohesion between the different CCUS activities; supporting the CCUS community to develop clear strategies and recommendations; accompanied by a strong continuous programme for outreach, dissemination and communication.

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

Authors:

Charles-Albert Bareth	Carbon Capture and Storage Association ASBL	2024-06-21
Line Rydså	SINTEF Energi AS	2024-06-21

Reviewed by:

Marie Bysveen	SINTEF Energi AS	2024-06-26
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Contact details:

+32 2 882 50 07

iwg9@zeroemissionsplatform.eu

www.ccus-setplan.eu

www.zeroemissionsplatform.eu

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1 PROJECT MANAGEMENT PLAN

D5.1 Project Management Plan (Month 5 and reviewed in Month 12 and Month 24).

1.1 Short summary

The Project Management Plan contains the relevant information required for project management.

This deliverable is public and contain info on the Gantt chart giving the deliverables and project timelines, as well as the work breakdown structure.

1.2 About project beneficiaries

There is an on-going process with project amendment to change a beneficiary from CCSA ASBL to ZEP-C (see full names in Chapter 2), but this depends on a decision from CINEA.

If the amendment request is supported by CINEA, implying a change a beneficiary from CSCA ASBL to ZEP-C, CCSA ASBL will be replaced with ZEP-C where this is mentioned in this document for reporting period 3 of the project (July 2024-June 2025).

1.3 Reporting periods

The project has three reporting periods (RP):

- Month 1-month 12, July 2022-June 2023
- Month 13-month 24, July2023-June 2024
- Month 25-month 36, July 2024-June 2025

Periodic reports to be submitted 60 days after the end of each reporting period.

RP1		RP2		RP3	
1	jul.22	13	jul.23	25	jul.24
2	aug.22	14	aug.23	26	aug.24
3	sep.22	15	sep.23	27	sep.24
4	okt.22	16	okt.23	28	okt.24
5	nov.22	17	nov.23	29	nov.24
6	des.22	18	des.23	30	des.24
7	jan.23	19	jan.24	31	jan.25
8	feb.23	20	feb.24	32	feb.25
9	mar.23	21	mar.24	33	mar.25
10	apr.23	22	apr.24	34	apr.25
11	mai.23	23	mai.24	35	mai.25
12	jun.23	24	jun.24	36	jun.25

2 SSZEPIWG9 - GANTT CHART / PROJECT STRUCTURE

An overview of project deliverables and project months. Version as of June 2024. Orange marks time for AC Plenary meetings.

Calendar month	2022						2023						2024						2025						Type	Lead	Support												
	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June				July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec						
Project month	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36			
Work Package 1: Delivery of the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan																																							
D1.1. Work programme, dissemination and communication plan							D1.1																														R	CCSA	
D1.2. Engagement programme											D1.2																										DEC	CCSA	
D1.3. Review of the ETIP/IWG and opportunities to increase future impacts																																					DEC	CCSA	SINTEF
D1.4. Review of the IWG9 R&I activities and targets																																					DEC	SINTEF	CCSA
D1.5. Recommendations regarding Certificates for Carbon Dioxide Removals																																					R	CCSA	
D1.6. Recommendations focusing on Social Sciences and Humanities expertise																																					R	CCSA	
Work Package 2: Coordination of Networks and Temporary Working Groups																																							
D2.1. Recommendations on CCUS R&I priorities for Horizon Europe work programme												D2.1																								R	SINTEF	CCSA	
D2.2. Annual progress reviews and recommendations on the 8 R&I activities													D2.2a																							R	SINTEF	CCSA	
D2.3. Insights on EU and national support instruments for CCUS R&I and deployment																																				R	CCSA	SINTEF	
D2.4. Report on key enablers and hurdles for CCS/CCU projects, focus on public perception																																				R	CCSA	SINTEF	
D2.5. Active support and recommendations to the European Commission CCUS Forum							D2.5a																													DEC	CCSA		
D2.6. Report on CDR, article 6 of the Paris agreement and the needed regulatory framework												D2.6																								R	CCSA		
Work Package 3: Support outreach and external relations																																							
D3.1. Outreach programmes and briefings with European institutions and Member States																																				DEC	CCSA		
D3.2. Develop the website												D3.2																								DEC	CCSA		
D3.3. Disseminate the knowledge developed through external workshop events.																																				DEC	CCSA		
D3.4. Present outputs and recommendations at SET Plan Steering Group events, other EC initiatives, etc.																																				DEC	CCSA	SINTEF	
D3.5. Develop presentation materials and give presentations at external conferences																																				R	CCSA		
Work Package 4: Support to the Government Group																																							
D4.1. Disseminate reports and recommendations to Member States													D4.1a																							R	CCSA		
D4.2. Input from national governments on the focus and outputs from the project																																				DEC	CCSA		
D4.3. Support from national governments on delivery of the Implementation Plan																																				DEC	CCSA		
Work Package 5: Management of the project																																							
D5.1. Project Management Plan							D5.1a																													OTHER	CCSA	SINTEF	
D5.2. Data management plan							D5.2																													R	CCSA	SINTEF	
D5.3. All obligations under the grant agreement																																				OTHER	SINTEF		
D5.4. Outputs for the work packages as requested by the ZEP AC and IWG9 Plenary																																				OTHER	CCSA		

2.1 Participants

- SINTEF Energi AS (SINTEF), NO 999513221, Coordinator
- The Carbon Capture and Storage Association ASBL (CCSA ASBL), BE 898779885 (beneficiary until 30 June 2024 – pending decision from CINEA)
- From 1 July: ZEP Communications ASBL (ZEP-C), pending decision from CINEA

2.2 List of Work Packages

Work package		Lead	Start Month	End
WP1	Delivery of the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan	CCSA ASBL	1	36
WP2	Coordination of Networks and Temporary Working Groups	CCSA ASBL	1	36
WP3	Support outreach and external relations	CCSA ASBL	1	36
WP4	Support to the Government Group	CCSA ASBL	1	36
WP5	Management of the project	SINTEF	1	36

2.3 Work Package descriptions

A description of the work packages can be found in the Grant Agreement Annex 1 Part A.

3 OBJECTIVES AND BACKGROUND

Interest from both private and public actors in Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage (CCUS) technologies has strongly increased in the last three years. The European Commission published the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy in February 2024, the first EU strategy dedicated to CCUS. The proposal for a regulation Net-Zero Industry Act published in 2023 aims to develop an EU market for CO₂ storage services. The impact assessment of the proposed EU 2040 climate target foresees a large role for CCUS that will require a very significant ramp-up in the coming years. France and Germany are preparing carbon management strategies at the national level with publications expected in 2024. Progress is also taking place in the private sector. Yara Sluiskil has taken a final investment decision in 2023 to transport CO₂ to the Northern Lights project. Finally, the construction of CCS facilities at the Asnæs and Avedøre power plants operated by Ørsted has started at the end of last year. The construction of Project Porthos is underway.

CCUS is entering its deployment phase. Large capture, transport, and storage projects need to be realised in the coming years to meet the EU objective of 50 million tonnes of CO₂ stored every year by 2030. This requires very large investments. The SET Plan Implementation Plan will be crucial in the next five years to develop and deploy CCS and CCU technologies, learn from operational projects, maintain research and innovation (R&I) activities, consolidate political and public support and accelerate the deployment of projects.

The overarching goal of this *project* is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platform (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan and its integrated roadmap – with a long-term perspective, beyond the period of *the project* (since ZEP and IWG9 are strong brands, we will use *‘the project’* instead of the acronym in this application).

To deliver this goal the *project* establishes the following objectives:

- Support the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders’ activities through the IWG9 and ETIP ZEP – also coordinating with other initiatives and projects – to ensure active engagement in implementing the SET Plan.
- Deepen participation and foster cooperation between stakeholders relevant to CCUS and the clean energy transition, including industry, research and universities, EU institutions, Member States, civil society, and international initiatives on the clean energy transition.
- Accelerate the clean energy transition by progressing the delivery of the CCUS R&I activities, based on defined cross-cutting aspects, and contributing to the development of a European Research Area (ERA) in the field of Energy.
- Engage all stakeholders in supporting the progress of emerging policy priorities at EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS.
- Develop and implement robust outreach approaches and engagement with societal actors for CCUS development and deployment, across the EU and associated countries.

Supporting the realisation of the SET Plan Implementation Plan on CCS and CCU

The SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group 9 on CCUS (IWG9) has defined 8 key Research and Innovation (R&I) activities with 10 linked targets to be met – approved by the SET Plan Steering Group. The previous activities were as follows:

- R&I Activity 1: Delivery of a whole chain CCS project operating in the power sector (target 1).
- R&I Activity 2: Delivery of regional CCS and CCU clusters, including feasibility for a European hydrogen infrastructure (targets 2 & 3 and 10).
- R&I Activity 3: EU Projects of Common Interest for CO₂ transport infrastructure (target 4).
- R&I Activity 4: Establish a European CO₂ Storage Atlas (target 5).
- R&I Activity 5: Unlocking European Storage capacity (target 7).
- R&I Activity 6: Developing next-generation CO₂ capture technologies (target 6).
- R&I Activity 7: CCU Action (targets 8 & 9).
- R&I Activity 8: Understanding and communicating the role of CCS and CCU in meeting European and national energy and climate change goals (target 10).

The previous targets were as follows:

1. Delivery of 15 commercial-scale CCS projects linked to industrial CO₂ sources. Further 10 projects having completed a FEED study and 5 having made an investment decision.
2. Delivery of 10 commercial-scale CCS projects for clean, flexible power and heat generation (including waste-to-energy plants), complementary to increased renewable energy generation in the energy mix.
3. EU Member States and external SET Plan countries having completed national and regional CCS roadmaps for the development of dedicated CO₂ transport infrastructure (new, retrofitted, and repurposed), including clusters of CO₂ sources and shared, cross-border CO₂ infrastructure. The infrastructure being included in the European Ten-Year Network Development Plan (TYNDP).
4. At least 10 additional EU Projects of Common Interest (PCI) for CO₂ transport infrastructure, with a focus on Central, Eastern, and Southern Europe. Experience from the first full-scale CCS project should be taken into account in the SET Plan activities linked to targets 3 and 4.
5. An up-to-date and detailed inventory of the most suitable and cost-effective geological storage capacity (based on agreed methodology), identified and accepted by various national authorities in Europe.
6. At least 3 pilots of capture technologies at TRL 7-8 in different industrial applications, including one enabling low-emission hydrogen production. At least 6 pilots of capture technologies at TRL 5-6, of which at least 2 pilots to test climate positive solutions such as Bio-CCS and direct air capture (DAC).
7. An interim target of at least 6 new CO₂ storage sites in preparation or operating in different settings (i.e. obtained or ready to submit an application for a storage permit). A target by 2030 of a further 9 sites to be appraised to the same level, in a range of geological settings, both onshore and offshore.
8. By 2030, several demonstration installations producing CO₂-based fuels, chemicals and materials at the scale of tens of kt/a and contributing to EU 2030 and 2050 climate and circularity objectives.
9. By 2030, first large-scale commercial installations enabled by a supportive regulatory framework and risk-sharing financial measures at national and EU level including IPCEIs in the context of new

industrial alliances mentioned in the New Industrial Strategy for Europe.

10. All European countries having identified, if applicable, the need for CCS/CCU as part of their strategy (producing a national CCS roadmap) for their transition towards net-zero by 2050 (included in their National Energy and Climate Plans).

The IWG9 has initiated the review of these targets and activities to reflect the growing importance of CCUS technologies to reach climate neutrality. This review is based on the significant policy targets described in the previous section. Targets and activities need to be revised to reflect the emergence of the CCUS market in the coming years and the large scale-up required under the European Commission climate modelling. Working groups dedicated to projects and infrastructure, CO₂ capture, CO₂ storage, and CCU have been set up to contribute to this review. Participants from different backgrounds (research, industry, NGOs...) have been invited to include a wider perspective on this review. The first working group meetings took place at the end of April and a first draft of the new targets and activities is under preparation for presentation at AC79/IWG9 Plenary on 19 June.

4 COORDINATED WORK UNDER ONE GOVERNANCE STRUCTURE

Coordination

The general concept is to establish a structure that facilitates effective cooperation and contribution of all relevant stakeholders to the SET Plan – to seek the participation of stakeholders in a broad, inclusive and transparent dialogue with the goal of establishing consensus on the required actions for the scale-up of CCUS. The work is conducted in an objective, transparent and robust way to promote the coherence of the stakeholders in the development of coordinated positions on the role of CCUS in the European energy system and to ensure trust in the technology. Transparency and trust are absolutely crucial. The deployment of CCUS will require large resources, including public funding. The possibility for external stakeholders to assess the merits of the technology and its value for climate action is a key element to support public perception and political support. In practice, this includes the possibility to access reports that are publicly available on the CCUS SET-Plan and ZEP website and to attend open meetings, including the IWG9 Plenary/ZEP Advisory Councils, the Policy & Economics Committee meetings, and the Technology Committee meetings.

The approach builds on and takes into account the strengths from the existing ETIP ZEP and IWG9 structures, that have been developed and approved by the stakeholders, combined with efficient coordination of the workstreams across these structures. This way, *the project* provides a very good basis to efficiently ensure that the work packages meet the needs and expectations of stakeholders in order to give appropriate support to the delivery of the SET Plan. The efficient coordination of these two bodies brings together stakeholders, including industrial sectors, academics and researchers, civil society and public stakeholders, including the European institutions and Member States governments.

- **The Advisory Council (AC)** is the body of ETIP ZEP members that meets quarterly, it is responsible for all decisions and sets the strategic direction for ETIP ZEP, oversees the work and deliverables etc., and guides on actions. AC members serve for a renewable three-year term and appoint a Chairperson and Vice Chairpersons. The Advisory Council Executive Committee (ACEC), consisting of ZEP Chair, Vice-Chairs and Co-Chairs for the Committees and ERC, is convened once per month to guide and take decisions between AC meetings.
- **The Plenary is the body of IWG9 members** that meets quarterly, oversees the work and deliverables etc., guides on actions, is responsible for all decisions and sets the strategic direction for the IWG9. The Plenary appoints three Chairpersons, of which two from country representatives and one representing ETIP ZEP.

The figure below represents the organisation of the Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP).

ETIP ZEP and IWG9 are supported under a common grant. In order to deliver as impactful a support as possible for the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan, *the project* is aligning and coordinating activities and measures. One of the challenges when coordinating activities between ETIP ZEP and IWG9 is that European countries (SET Plan countries) are members of the IWG9, while they can only be observers in ETIP ZEP – since representatives from country governments and authorities cannot be involved in deciding on the ETIP’s positions and views on specific EU or Member State policy, legislation, funding mechanisms, etc. Taking this into account, *the project* will use and coordinate the strengths of the stakeholders and governance from both structures, bringing forward aligned and coordinated activities in an efficient way, *see structure above*.

The quarterly meetings of the AC and Plenary are held back-to-back on the same day – open to all CCUS stakeholders and representatives of the EU institutions – to increase knowledge sharing and ensure support to and enhanced coordination of the stakeholders. The agendas are coordinated with joint send-outs ahead of the meetings, including the agendas and pre-reads for both meetings, all to enhance coordination of stakeholders. The AC meeting/AC members decides on matters that are specific to ETIP ZEP, while the IWG9 Plenary decides on matters that are specific to the SET-Plan Implementation Plan.

ZEP has additional resources from its membership to enhance the quantity and quality of relevant activities. This includes, among others, communication and advocacy activities provided by ZEP-C ASBL.

Well established and efficient governance and way of working

The work of ETIP ZEP and IWG9 is supported by the secretariat, guided and undertaken by three Committees and their associated Working Groups and Temporary Working Groups (TWG), as well as the External Relations Group and the Government Group (GG). Each Committee and the GG meets three times per year and the ERC eight times per year.

- **Policy and Economics Committee (P&EC)** and linked **TWGs** will focus on the political economy. In the European Commission’s Industrial Carbon Management Strategy, the European Commission “recognises that industrial carbon management technologies are part of the solution towards

achieving climate neutrality by 2050” adding that “these technologies are needed to continue reducing and managing carbon emissions in industrial processes in the EU, notably where mitigation options are limited.”. The work of ETIP ZEP/IWG9 is therefore embedded in a policy scenario where the EU needs to deliver on 2040 and 2050 climate objectives. Coordination with Member States, EU policymakers and the different parts of the CCUS value chain – represented in the ETIP ZEP/IWG9 membership – is crucial to ensure that these technologies can become operational by 2030 and to support the EU’s decarbonisation pathway.

- **Technology Committee (TC)** and linked **TWGs** will focus on CCS/CCU technologies. As CCS and CCU technologies are becoming operational and are integrated in Europe’s industrial value chain, it will be vital to keep a focus on technological developments and ensure that these are shared within and beyond the CCUS community. Technology developments are foreseeable in all the segments of the value chain – capture, transport, storage, and utilisation. Technical reports will be needed to assess the continuous developments on CCS and CCU and offer an overview on the current status of the technologies. The Committee supports continued work on the prioritised R&I activities, crucial to bring down costs, improve efficiency and solve barriers and challenges for upcoming and planned projects. Recent work includes the organisation of a webinar in May 2024 dedicated to the mapping of CO₂ storage capacity in Europe. This webinar was attended by 340 people and should be accompanied by a paper with technical recommendations. Upcoming work includes a report on CCS and power generation, including the potential role of CCS to reduce dependencies on critical raw materials.
- The **ZEP Projects Network (PNW)** focuses on supporting CCS/CCU market-ready projects. An ever-rising number of CCS/CCU projects are progressing towards becoming operational by mid to late 2020s. These are projects in all parts of the value chain, linked to industrial processes, combined with the production of low-carbon hydrogen, some offering the possibility to remove CO₂ from the atmosphere, etc. The first edition took place in Rotterdam in January 2024, witnessed strong attendance and received positive feedback from participants. Dedicated sessions allowed the Porthos project to share its learnings with other projects from a technical and financial standpoint. A second edition is planned at the end of 2024. The first edition showed the importance of fostering on-the-ground information exchange and to facilitate discussions between project developers.
- **The External Relations Committee (ERC)** is merged with the previous Communications group. Outreach towards the European institutions and national governments will be pursued and increased to further communicate on the role of CCS and CCU in achieving the EU’s climate goals. Given the increasing international climate awareness – with approximately 90 percent of the world economy having announced net-zero GHG emissions targets by mid-century and there about – and increasing interest in CCUS technology, the *project* engages in international collaboration with existing CCUS initiatives – such as the Mission Innovation, the Clean Energy Ministerial CCUS, the ERA-NET ACT, etc. The European Parliament elections in June 2024 will be a point of focus in upcoming activities. Additional work includes the organisation of a ZEP Conference in December 2024 and a webinar dedicated to public perception in June 2024.
- **The Government Group (GG)** appoints its own members, operates independently from the ZEP Advisory Council and meets four times per year. While national government representatives are directly involved in the work on delivering the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan, through the

IWG9, they can only be observers in ETIP ZEP – since they cannot be involved in deciding on positions or views on specific EU or Member State policy, legislation or funding mechanisms. With the ongoing operationalisation of projects and the large ramp-up required to meet the injection capacity objective under the Net-Zero Industry Act, interaction with the GG will be crucial: input and support on the work and the delivery of the Implementation Plan, as well as dissemination of project outputs and recommendations. Members of the GG will be invited to attend meetings of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG Plenary. Government Group meetings take place online and in a hybrid fashion when hosted by a national government. Hybrid meetings allow for site visits and in-person discussions that facilitate the engagement and cooperation between Member States. An upcoming Government Group meeting in September 2024 will take place in Dunkirk (France) and include the visit of the DMX pilot, the future CO₂ transport terminal, and the ArcelorMittal steel plant.

- The Committees and ERC will guide and drive the support to deliver the R&I activities and updated targets identified in the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan/IWG9. This will draw on the experience and knowledge sharing from the iterative process where CCS and CCU R&I projects address specific challenges with the results implemented in large-scale projects, which then will identify new challenges that can best be solved by undertaking R&I activities. The described challenges for CCS and CCU development for the coming years are:
 - Accelerating timely deployment at scale of CCS and CCU technologies.
 - Driving costs down – through R&I, learning by doing and economies of scale.
 - Identifying potential critical raw material dependencies.
 - Enabling rapid scale-up to deliver on the climate goals.
 - Enabling EU citizens to make informed choices regarding the benefits that CCS and CCU bring.

Terms of References for TWGs, timelines and participation are approved by the AC/Plenary to complete specific work packages under the guidance of the Networks. The Committees and TWGs will be populated by experts from different organisations (industry, research, NGOs...). Committees and TWGs are crucial for knowledge sharing and interaction with key stakeholders, which will be further strengthened by outreach, communication and dissemination activities.

Transparency

The project is not a research project and will, thus, not bring new research data; however, the methodology for *the project* is based on full transparency. Meetings and seminars are open and all documentation, reports, papers, results, dissemination and communication will be made freely available to all interested parties via a dedicated project website as a continuous part of *the project* during its lifetime. Data contained in the documentation, reports, papers etc. will be comprehensively referenced to ensure that users can interpret and verify the conclusions of *the project*. Together with the stakeholders, a long-term repository for the information will be identified to ensure that the information is available beyond the period of *the project*.

4.1 Deliverables

The list of deliverables can be found in the beginning of this chapter.

R: Document, report

DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc

A list of deliverable descriptions can also be found in the Grant Agreement Annex 1 Part A.

Deliverables will either in its entirety be approved by the AC/Plenary (e.g. a specific report) or they will include several already approved reports, papers, webinars, etc.

Deliverables will be treated as other workstreams: ToRs will be drafted by the secretariat in cooperation with TWG co-chairs and the relevant Committee and brought to the AC and or Plenary for approval. The secretariat will together with the co-chairs coordinate and support the workstream (and specific TWG), prepare the deliverable for approval, and upload the deliverable to the *project* SharePoint (joint between SINTEF and CCSA ASBL).

The quality of the deliverables will be guaranteed by the co-chairs (and TWG of experts), the secretariat, the process itself, and the approval by the AC/Plenary.

About additional deliverables: given that fast-moving development of CCUS – the work programme being based on the EU (and Member States' policy and funding agenda) – new reports will be added and there might be adjustments needed. Proposed new reports will be approved by the AC and or Plenary before formal preparation.

4.2 List of milestones

The basis for the *project's* milestones is the quarterly meetings of the AC and Plenary (marked in orange below). Draft meeting minutes will be uploaded to the *project* SharePoint (joint between SINTEF and CCSA ASBL). Milestone due date is shifted +1 to align with AC Plenary meeting dates.

		2022					2023												2024												2025							
Calendar month		July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	
Project month		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	Lead
M1	M1 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary			M1																																	CCSA ASBL	
M2	M2 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary					M2																															CCSA ASBL	
M3	M3 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary									M3																											CCSA ASBL	
M4	M4 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary											M4																									CCSA ASBL	
M5	M5 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary													M5																							CCSA ASBL	
M6	M6 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary															M6																					CCSA ASBL	
M7	M7 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary																	M7																			CCSA ASBL	
M8	M8 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary																		M8																		CCSA ASBL	
M9	M9 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary																			M9																	CCSA ASBL	
M10	M10 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary																				M10																CCSA ASBL	
M11	M11 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary																					M11																CCSA ASBL
M12	M12 Meeting of the ZEP Advisory Council and the IWG9 Plenary																																M12	CCSA ASBL				

5 COMMUNICATION AND OUTREACH - DISSEMINATION

Communication and outreach for the *project* is based the ERC, as described above. These two groups meet every sixth week to guide and coordinate the activities. Needed approvals, as well as follow-up and reporting of the activities is done by/to the AC/Plenary (and to the ACEC between the AC meetings).

Dissemination of *project* results to policymakers, other stakeholders and the wider public, is done continuously, through in-person and online meetings, direct emails and newsletters, conferences, seminars and workshops, website, social media, etc. There is also a specific direct communication with European Governments through the Government Group.

Internal communication between SINTEF and CCSA ASBL is done at a dedicated SharePoint Project room.

6 WORK PROGRAMME 2024

The Carbon Capture & Storage Association (CCSA) plans to handover its role as project beneficiary to ZEP-C ASBL on 1 July 2024. ZEP-C ASBL would take over the execution of the project. SINTEF Energi AS would remain coordinator under the project. ZEP-C ASBL and SINTEF Energi AS are therefore foreseen to execute this work programme from July 2024. This is all pending an approval of the amendment to CINEA.

The work programme is developed by the secretariat in coordination with the co-chairs of the different Committees in order to reflect the activities that should be undertaken in the upcoming year. Technical reports, position papers, responses to consultations, and webinars are work items that can fall under the various committees. The work programme reflects as best as possible developments expected in the upcoming year, such as the annual edition of the Industrial Carbon Management Forum, the foreseen publication of legislative and policy proposals or elections.

The drafting of this programme starts in the autumn ahead of the IWG9 Plenary/Advisory Council of December. The draft work programme for the upcoming year is sent as a pre-read to the members of the IWG9 Plenary/Advisory Council. Pre-reads are sent one week before the meeting itself, which allows participants to read and analyse the draft work programme. During the IWG9 Plenary/Advisory Council, the work programme is presented, for instance by the ZEP secretary-general, and the Chair asks the IWG9 Plenary/Advisory Council to approve the draft work programme. Once approved, the work programme can be formally used.

The drafting of the 2025 work programme can start in the autumn 2024, asking the different committee co-chairs for input. This draft would be finalised end of November and presented for approval at the IWG9 Plenary/Advisory Council in December 2024.

ZEP and IWG9 Work Programme 2024

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7 INTRODUCTION

2024 will be an important year for the carbon capture and storage (CCS) community in Europe. The spade will go into the ground for the first commercial CCS site in the EU (Porthos in the Netherlands), Northern Lights will become the first project to deliver cross-border CO₂ transport and storage, the European Commission launches the long-awaited Industrial Carbon Management Strategy, there are elections for the European Parliament and Member States need to review their National Energy and Climate Plans. After many lost years, CCS seems to finally be moving from development to deployment as a key technology to drive the decarbonisation of Europe's hard-to-abate sectors.

The Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP) and the Implementation Working Group 9 of the SET-Plan (IWG9) are at the forefront of CCS policy making, on the one hand as the trusted advisors to the EU and as Member States working collectively to achieve Europe's climate goals – notably on the decarbonisation of the energy intensive industries. In this document, we provide an outline of our main activities for 2024.

The governance structures of ZEP and IWG9 are largely merged, and their secretariat is funded by a single Horizon Europe grant (running from July 2022 to June 2025), hence the choice for a joint work programme. We will also include those activities that are *de facto* funded by the members of ZEP, resulting in extra bandwidth for a programme that goes beyond the deliverables set out in the Horizon Europe grant agreement. For the sake of clarity, those deliverables for 2024 will be spelt out in detail below.

The work programme should be considered as a living and reference document, especially for those active in the various working groups as well as for the secretariat and the organisations executing the grant. It could also be changed depending on the outcome of the ZEP restructuring – a process underway now and should be implemented in 2024. As ZEP aims to strengthen its advocacy and communications workstream, this could alter the goals and deliverables of this work programme. Hence, a certain amount of flexibility and agility should be taken into account.

8 MAIN POLICY DEVELOPMENTS IN 2024

Before we dive into the work streams, let's zoom out and look at the main CCS and CCU related policy developments that we expect to happen in 2024.

In Q1 2024, the European Commission is expected to publish a proposal for an EU 2040 climate target. ZEP expects the proposal to provide further clarity on the role of CCS and CCU in contributing to the EU's climate targets, seeks to inform the co-decision process on the 2040 target and contribute to the upcoming legislative processes where existing EU legislation will be aligned with the 2040 target.

The 2040 climate target proposal will be complemented by an **Industrial Carbon Management Strategy (ICMS)**. The ICMS will assess what role CCS and CCU technologies can play in reducing and removing emissions in the EU economy until 2050, as well as what measures are needed to scale them up, including in the deployment of EU-wide CO₂ transport and storage infrastructures. This strategy will be crucial to set out the European Commission's vision on the role of CCS in Europe and what policy measures are needed to achieve this vision. The new Commission, expected to start at the end of 2024, is expected to propose policy initiatives supporting CCS.

- ZEP will continue to advocate for a strong ICMS in line with ZEP's recommendations on the strategy, as specified in [the contribution](#) to the ICMS consultation of 2023.
- If a consultation is opened following the publication of the strategy, ZEP will respond to the consultation.
- ZEP is ready to engage and support the Commission in the potential deliverables or initiatives proposed in the ICMS, provided that these align and enhance ZEP's impact in the deployment of CCS and CCU technologies

A landmark piece of legislation for CCS will undoubtedly be the **Net Zero Industry Act**, proposed by the Commission in early 2023. This proposal for a regulation will be under negotiation between the EU institutions (trilogues) in late 2023/early 2024. The two key elements in the NZIA are the 50Mt CO₂ annual injection capacity target for the EU in 2030 and its Article 18. Together with other stakeholders, the ZEP published [an open letter](#) in July 2023 calling for an implementable and pragmatic Net Zero Industry Act Article 18.

- ZEP will continue its support for the NZIA as it will spur the deployment of CCS in Europe. The NZIA should be approved before the **2024 European Parliament** elections. ZEP will insist on this timeline in its contact with policymakers.
- ZEP will make recommendations to the three institutions during the trilogues regarding the provisions best placed to support CCS deployment in Europe.

The European Parliament elections will take place from 6 to 9 June 2024. A new European Parliament entails a new European Commission. Both institutions will play a critical role in translating the 2040 climate targets into the right political and regulatory framework. As CCS will play an important role in achieving these climate targets, the Zero Emissions Platform seeks a (pro)active dialogue with the Commission and the Parliament, pushing for an ambitious CCS

agenda in the next EU legislative cycle. The ICMS is an obvious lever for such an agenda, but more political pressure will be needed.

- ZEP will further develop its advocacy and communications strategy and undertake efforts to have CCS represented in programmes of the main European political parties and the new European Commission's policy agenda.
- ZEP will engage with EU policymakers ahead of the elections to highlight the importance of CCS and CCU deployment and the need to develop EU and national funding programmes that fit the requirements to reach climate neutrality by 2050.

On the national level, EU member states are required to send updated **National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs)** to the Commission. The Guidance to Member States encourages national governments to include CCS provisions^[1]. Several Member States are in the process of developing their own carbon management strategies, such as Germany and France, while others are only beginning to explore CCS strategies (such as Spain).

- Together with other stakeholders, ZEP will analyse the updated NECPs and provide feedback on those NECPs where policies are insufficient and/or lacking.
- Pending internal capacity, ZEP will work with national governments to support them in their development of national carbon management strategies.

The European Commission published the Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform (STEP) proposal for a regulation at the end of June 2023 to support investments in critical technologies, such as CCS and CCU. An agreement on this proposal could take place in Q1 2024.

- ZEP will monitor the legislative progress of the STEP proposal and support the increase in the Innovation Fund and Horizon Europe programmes.
- ZEP will support the STEP proposal and highlight the need to develop EU and national funding programmes and to incentivise investments in line with the funding required for CCS to reach the 2040 and 2050 climate targets.

8.1 CCUS Forum

ZEP is one of the co-chairs of the CCUS Forum working group on CO₂ infrastructure and has contributed to several CCUS Forum working groups.

- ZEP will support the preparation of the 2024 plenary.
- ZEP will support and contribute to the potential future work of the CCUS Forum working group on CO₂ infrastructure and the CCUS Forum expert group on CO₂ specifications.

8.2 CDR

The European Commission published a proposal for a regulation on an EU certification for carbon removals in November 2022. Trilogues on the proposal have started start in Q4 2023 and policymakers are committed to reach an agreement before the European Parliament recesses in

March 2024. Following the adoption of the regulation, the European Commission, in collaboration with a dedicated expert group, will work on the preparation of a methodologies for carbon dioxide removals (CDR) certification framework throughout 2024.

- ZEP will closely monitor the progress of the proposal and will make policy recommendations, where useful.
- ZEP will contribute to the preparation of a CDR methodologies via its representative in the Expert Group, Kristin Jordal, and by responding to future potential calls for inputs.

ZEP will also follow the adoption of delegated acts amending the EU ETS Monitoring and Reporting Regulation and relevant for CCS and CCU deployment.

Finally, ZEP will closely monitor developments related to key EU funding programmes, including the Connecting Europe Facility, the Innovation Fund, Horizon Europe, and LIFE.

9 ZEP AND IWG9 COMMITTEES

Several hundreds of CCS experts meet regularly in meetings that the secretariat organises – mostly in the context of ZEP but also in combined sessions with IWG9 delegates. The main meetings continue to be the **Advisory Council** which gathers four times per year and is attended by ZEP members, the IWG9 constituency but also by interested parties that are not formally connected to either organisation. In June 2024, the Advisory Council will include a meeting of the **ZEP Communications ASBL** that gathers once a year. (This is the Belgian non-profit organisation with a membership structure that sponsors the ZEP secretariat and additional activities, on top of the EU grant).

Depending on political and economic developments, these are the most important work items per forum. The ZEP secretariat runs several bodies where members meet, both of the ZEP and of IWG9: Committees, Temporary Working Groups (which fall under Committees), and a new Projects Network. It also provides the secretariat for the ZEP Government Group, which consists of representatives of around twenty European governments.

9.1 Policy & Economics Committee

The Policy & Economics Committee (P&EC) will organise four meetings in 2024; all foreseen meetings should be virtual. The WG Policy & Funding is the main group driving policy work (including position papers, consultations, etc.).

9.2 Technology Committee

The Technology Committee (TC) will organise four meetings in 2024; the meeting taking place in or close to September will be an in-person meeting in Brussels; the other three will be virtual meetings.

Mission Innovation CDR. TC supports the EC in their participation in Mission Innovation on CDR. This has been an ongoing activity in 2023 and will be continued in 2024. The TWG CDR will meet regularly, guided by activities in the MI CDR. The work in the Removals Expert Group is part of this activity.

One report is currently in the pipeline. The TWG will continue their work and finalise their reports in 2024. The TWG CCS supply chain has been suspended. Remaining work includes:

- **Flexible power with CCS** (tbc, co-leads Arthur Heberle, Robert de Kler)

Topics for approval by the AC:

1. Transport cost: recent publications suggest that transport costs for landlocked emitters may reach €200/t, for the CO₂ to reach a coastline by rail and/or pipeline. A ZEP paper could be written on this topic, to highlight the issues and suggest ways forward (e.g., stressing the need for onshore storage). Just as with the aforementioned two reports, there is a capacity issue within the secretariat

2. CO₂ specifications: way forward. Recent development in the knowledge of the effects of and behaviour of impurities in CO₂ streams have led to strict specifications. This leads to increasing cost of purification for emitters, potentially making CCS unaffordable. A two-pipe solution to handle captured CO₂ from different capture technologies has also been suggested. The CCUS Forum expert group that produced the report for the CCUS-Forum could be invited to reflect on these issues.

9.3 Projects Network

In 2023 ZEP created the Projects Network that will support the many ongoing and planned CCS and CCU projects in Europe. The Network should also address existing barriers and help de-risking investments, improve public perception of CCS, and enable real project-to-project knowledge sharing. By introducing this network, ZEP establishes an important tool to efficiently support projects and, at the same time, actively help the EC and European governments regarding necessary policy/regulation, funding and actions linked to public perception.

The Projects Network is in development and will be launched officially at the Porthos site in Rotterdam, 24-25 January 2024. For the rest of the year, one or two more of such events could be organised in order to facilitate the exchange of knowledge among project developers and keep the momentum.

At the CCUS Forum 2023, the European Commission unveiled plans to launch their own industrial carbon management knowledge sharing network where participation will be mandatory for projects that have received EU funding, and voluntary and encouraged for others. Once the ICMS has been published and further details are known, ZEP will explore the options of informing this

new initiative via its own Projects Network experience to date and if dedicated funding is available, consider bidding to provide the secretariat for the Commission's network, streamlining the two initiatives into one.

The current ZEP Project Network does not have dedicated funding source, has been having challenges in confirming co-chairs and the detailed governance structure is yet to be established. However, if the future entails joining forces with the European Commission's network, these challenges would be addressed.

9.4 External Relations Committee

The External Relations Group plays a crucial role in providing strategic guidance to ZEP's external communications activities, as well as in promoting ZEP's mission and identity across its wide network of stakeholders. The ERG co-chairs also contribute to the development of external engagements with policymakers and are able to represent ZEP at these meetings.

Effective coordination between ERG and ACEC as well as the other committees is important to ensure the external facing activities are timely, focussed and effective.

Three main pillars identified:

- 1) Organisational (internal)
 - Work on clear Terms of Reference and Governance for ERG in its new configuration
 - Ensure that interaction /coordination with the other ZEP Committees is clearly organised, efficient, and effective (e.g. with ACEC, Policy & Economics, Government, etc)

- 2) External – socialisation of Policy /Technical work of ZEP Committees with relevant stakeholders
 - Develop and tailor an advocacy and communication plan based on the work program of the ZEP Committees by its January 2023 meeting – the plan needs to be fit for purpose and not too generic
 - Ensure a throughout review of the communication tools and practices (stakeholder mapping, messaging, use of social media, website, etc) to ensure an effective implementation of the external relations and communication program

- 3) External: Assess potential role of ZEP in the area of public acceptance:
 - Education (for example in the Parliament after elections, with local authorities in Member states, in schools and universities)
 - Support (including to authorities / local authorities) with communication materials, events, etc to reach the general public

As highlighted in the introduction, the work programme covers activities funded by the Horizon Europe grant and those funded by member sponsorships to ZEP-Communications ABSL. Following

from “additional work programme”, adopted by ZEP for 2023 for activities funded by member sponsorships, the 2024 work programme covers all both grant- and member-funded activities. In 2023, the focus of activities funded by member sponsorships was advocacy, communications, events and visibility. 2024 work programme continues this approach, and these activities are likely to overwhelmingly fit under the External Relation Committee’s activities:

- Establishing an advocacy and communications implementation plan with clear KPIs
 - Establishing specific goals for engaging with policymakers on CCS-related policy files
 - Establishing renewed brand voice and messages for ZEP that is used uniformly in all communication – what the organisation does, its principles, its value proposition for members
 - Increase ZEP visibility across social media platforms
 - Explore rebranding ZEP and revamping ZEP website
 - Raising the profile of CCS as a climate technology

- Organising annual ZEP CCS Conference in April 2024

10 WORK ON RESEARCH AND INNOVATION UNDER THE IMPLEMENTATION WORKING GROUP 9

From SETIS:

- *The European Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET Plan) is a key stepping stone to boost the transition towards a climate-neutral energy system through the development of low-carbon technologies in a fast and competitive way.*
- *The SET Plan was established in 2007 and since the creation of the energy union in 2015, it became one of the main instruments of the energy union’s 5th pillar on research innovation and competitiveness.*
- *By improving new technologies and bringing down their costs through coordinated national research efforts, the SET Plan helps promote cooperation among EU countries, companies and research institutions. It does so by helping to coordinate national research and innovation activities in developing low-carbon energy among EU countries and associated countries, as well as aligning national research and innovation programmes with its agenda.*

The [SET plan activities](#) are clustered into 10 actions for research and innovation, whereas CCUS is number 9 (thereby the number 9 in the SET Plan Implementation Working Group, IWG, for CCUS):

1. Performant renewable technologies integrated in energy system
2. Reduce costs of technologies:
3. New smart technologies and services for consumers
4. Resilience and security of the energy system
5. New materials and technologies for energy efficiency solutions for buildings:
6. Energy efficiency for industry:
7. Competitive in global battery sector and e-mobility
8. Renewable fuels and bioenergy:
9. Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage
10. Nuclear Safety

The [CCUS SET Plan Implementation Working Group \(IWG9\)](#) is chaired by the Netherlands, Norway and the Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP) and established a few years ago ambitious 2030 targets and R&I activities. These are now ready for updating – and this work will be carried out in 2024. The European Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET Plan) established 10 priority actions, covering a wide range of technologies, including one focused on carbon capture and storage (CCS) and carbon capture and utilisation (CCU) (action 9). Each priority action has developed an Implementation Plan which outlines clear targets, alongside the Research and Innovation (R&I) activities needed to achieve them. The progress of the Implementation Plans is monitored by Implementation Working Groups (IWG) and the IWG9 focuses on CCS/CCU. The SET Plan is expected to grow in importance in view of the upcoming EU regulation Net-Zero Industry Act.

The IWG9 monitors progress on CCS/CCU. In 2016, the European Commission, the SET Plan countries, and industry agreed on 10 targets for CCS and CCU for 2030. These were updated in 2020 (link to the [past 10 targets](#)) to reflect better the direction of the sector, including the challenges ahead.

The IWG9 Strategic Coordination Group oversees the revision of the R&I targets and activities and coordinates the work of the different working groups (full-scale projects, clusters and infrastructure; CO₂ capture, CO₂ storage, and CO₂ utilisation). The two IWG9 co-chairs from the Netherlands and Norway and the working group co-chairs constitute the Strategic Coordination Group. The working groups gather representatives from industry, research, NGOs, and civil servants to work in cooperation on new targets and activities that better reflect the current policy landscape, recent research developments, industry needs, and the overall climate ambitions. Working groups met in April 2024 and are due to meet again in September/November 2024. With support from the secretariat, the co-chairs gather input during working group meetings and propose new R&I targets and activities. First drafts have been developed as of June 2024 and are due to progress ahead of their approval at the IWG9 plenary in December 2024.

In addition to these formal bodies of the SET Plan on CCUS, it is important to engage widely in all corners of this triangle – ranging from industry, R&I and governments – for the impact of the SET Plan work to increase.

An important part of the ZEP/IWG9 work is to advance the research and innovation agenda of CC(U)S in Europe. Notably within the IWG9 context, European countries should be more involved and exchange their latest insights of R&I projects.

At the EU grant preceding the current one for the secretariat of IWG9, a clear research agenda was spelled out; below follows a similar structure to organise the ZEP/IWG9 in this respect. Notably, ZEP will support the realisation of the SET Plan Implementation Plan on CCS and CCU which has defined eight key R&I activities with ten linked targets to be met.

The secretariat will increase its engagement with European governments to find more CCS R&I contact points and add these to our distribution lists.

The R&I Activities included in the existing [SET Plan Implementation Plan for CCUS](#), and that need to be updated, are the following (in brackets are reference made to R&I targets to be explained in the following section):

- R&I Activity 1: Delivery of a whole chain CCS project operating in the power sector (target 1).
- R&I Activity 2: Delivery of regional CCS and CCU clusters, including feasibility for a European hydrogen infrastructure (targets 2 & 3 and 10).
- R&I Activity 3: EU Projects of Common Interest for CO₂ transport infrastructure (target 4).
- R&I Activity 4: Establish a European CO₂ Storage Atlas (target 5).
- R&I Activity 5: Unlocking European Storage capacity (target 7).
- R&I Activity 6: Developing next-generation CO₂ capture technologies (target 6).
- R&I Activity 7: CCU Action (targets 8 & 9).
- R&I Activity 8: Understanding and communicating the role of CCS and CCU in meeting European and national energy and climate change goals (target 10).

How to do this:

In the period 2019-2022 a separate grant supported the work of the SET Plan Implementation Working Group on CCUS, namely the [IMPACTS9 project](#), coordinated by CCSA. The secretariat work of the CCUS SET Plan targets was implemented in the following way:

With reference to the CCUS SET plan 2030 targets, the work in 2019-2022 was organised in five sub-groups below with the responsibility to follow up the Targets listed below each sub-group:

In the following year the plan is to organise this work in stronger collaboration with existing structures in ZEP (especially the Technology Committee) and EERA JP CCS. In practice this will be reported back to the ZEP AC/IWG) plenary meetings quarterly.

11 DELIVERABLES OF THE HORIZON EUROPE GRANT

As stipulated in the EU grant agreement, ZEP and IWG9 need to complete the following deliverables in 2024. It will be a priority for the ZEP secretariat and SINTEF to not delay any of the following deliverables.

11.1 Work Package 1: Delivery of the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan

D1.4 Review of the IWG9 R&I activities and targets

Deadline June 2024, lead SINTEF, input IWG9 needed

D1.6 Recommendations focusing on Social Sciences and Humanities expertise

Deadline July 2024, lead CCSA

Based on the work on CCS/CCU projects, enablers and hurdles for new CCS and CCU projects, provide recommendations focusing on Social Sciences and Humanities expertise.

11.2 Work Package 2: Coordination of Networks and Temporary Working Groups

D2.2 Annual progress reviews and recommendations on the 8 R&I activities

Deadline May 2024, lead SINTEF, input IWG9 needed

Provide recommendations on the steps required to deliver each of the eight key IWG9 Research and Innovation (R&I) activities – providing an annual review of progress and where applicable including recommendations.

D2.4 Report on key enablers and hurdles for CCS/CCU projects, focus on public perception

Deadline February 2024, lead CCSA

Develop report on key enablers and hurdles for European CCS/CCU projects, with a focus on public perception.

11.3 Work Package 3: Support outreach and external relations

D3.1 Outreach programmes and briefings with European institutions and Member States

Deadline November 2024, lead CCSA

Prepare outreach programmes, plan and hold briefings with officials from the European institutions and Member States on output and conclusions from the project's technical, policy, regulatory, and economic work.

D3.4 Present outputs and recommendations at SET Plan Steering Group events, other EC initiatives, etc.

Deadline August 2024, lead CCSA

Present outputs at SET Plan Steering Group events and provide recommendations to other European Commission initiatives – e.g. Innovation Fund Expert Group and the European Clean Hydrogen Alliance, the Clean Energy Transition Partnership, the High Level Group on Energy Intensive Industries – and other international initiatives, e.g. Mission Innovation and the Clean Energy Ministerial.

11.4 Work Package 4: Support to the Government Group

D4.1 Disseminate reports and recommendations to Member States

Deadline November 2024, lead CCSA

Disseminate reports and recommendations to Member State representatives.

D4.2 Input from national governments on the focus and outputs from the project

Deadline June 2024, lead CCSA

Input from national governments on the focus and development of reports and other outputs from the project.

D4.3 Support from national governments on delivery of the Implementation Plan

Deadline June 2024, lead CCSA

Support from national governments on delivery of the Implementation Plan.

11.5 Work Package 5: Management of the project

D5.1 Project Management Plan

Deadline June 2024, lead CCSA

Project Management Plan with a Gantt chart and a Work Breakdown Structure. (review)

Further contact

Joop Hazenberg

Secretary General, ZEP

Joop.hazenberg@zeroemissionsplatform.eu

+32 496 70 36 38

^[1] [Guidance to Member States for updated NECPs 2021-2030](#), European Commission.

12 SSZEPIWG9 INTERNAL GOVERNANCE STRUCTURE

The Consortium Agreement section 6 notes the General Assembly (GA) to be the decision-making body of the consortium. The GA will meet once every six months, chaired by the coordinator.

Partner	Authorised member	Deputy
SINTEF	Mona Mølnevik	
CCSA ASBL	Ruth Herbert	

The Management Team will meet once a month to discuss project operations.

SINTEF	CCSA ASBL
Marie Bysveen (Primary Coordinator Contact, PCC)	Joop Hazenberg
Line Rydså (Project Manager, PM)	Charles-Albert Bareth
Optional: Amy Brunsvold	

One person is appointed as WP-leader This person comes from the Beneficiary who is responsible for the WP (WP lead).

WP	Lead Beneficiary	WP-leader
WP1	CCSA ASBL	Joop Hazenberg
WP2	CCSA ASBL	Joop Hazenberg
WP3	CCSA ASBL	Joop Hazenberg
WP4	CCSA ASBL	Joop Hazenberg
WP5	SINTEF	Line Rydså